

ADAPTING TO THE NEW NORMAL: OVERCOMING CHALLENGES IN THE ELEMENTARY GRADE TEACHERS' IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 3

Pages: 288-296

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1860

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11303603

Manuscript Accepted: 05-01-2024

Adapting to the New Normal: Overcoming Challenges in the Elementary Grade Teachers' Implementation of Modular Distance Learning

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Abstract

This study examined the difficulties faced and coping methods used by public elementary school teachers as they implemented modular distance learning, or MDL, in the context of the new normal. Six participants in this phenomenological study were selected following specific criteria for purposive sampling at Tuhian Elementary School. This study used a self-devised, semi-structured interview guide with two parts as its research instrument. Four master educators with Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) degrees attested to its validity. After the interview, the recorded responses were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted to provide answers to the questions posed in this undertaking using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Meanwhile, findings concurred that the challenges are inevitable; for, teachers encountered challenges regarding the implementation of MDL, which include the following: (a) late submission of self-learning modules and learning activity sheets submissions; (b) missing self-learning modules and learning activity sheets, (c) tracking and assessing the development of learners through summative and formative evaluation, (d) ignorance brought on by inadequate lack of communication channels, (e) uncooperative and unresponsive parents, and (f) lack of training inadequate internet access, time constraint, and distance from school. In regard, they employed coping mechanism strategies to address the challenges they encountered, which include, being optimistic, resilient, and enhancing collaborative skills. Based on the results of the study, an improved coping mechanism framework was developed.

Keywords: *modular distance learning, challenges encountered, coping mechanism*

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) announced in January 2020 that there was an outbreak of the coronavirus disease of 2019 (COVID-19) is a global public health emergency that caused some school closures as early as March 2020, impacting 91% of students worldwide. In light of the significance of the ongoing increase of confirmed cases, governments worldwide turned to learning continuity plans to maintain schooling despite the pandemic. Teachers made use of instructional techniques that spared the students from the pandemic's threat but will enable students to carry on learning even in the face of danger. In addition to producing health concerns globally, the COVID-19 pandemic is having an impact on every aspect of life, including education (World Bank, 2020). In the new normal setup, it has presented tough scenarios for educational institutions to continuously give learners from various nations with relevant and substantial learning.

On the other hand, the DepEd must be creative and resourceful in providing high-quality, easily accessible, pertinent, and liberating education given the serious threat the pandemic poses. Because of this, the BE-LCP was created to guarantee that learners receive their learning opportunities in a secure manner. DepEd has issued directives on flexible learning and resources in compliance with this, including DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019 or the K-12 Basic Education Program Policy Guidelines, which provide adaptable learning materials that consider the needs, context, situations, and diversity of learners. The purpose of these policy guidelines is to establish requirements and criteria for the distribution of educational materials in the BE-LCP implementation process. Under the supervision of responsible people and with ongoing monitoring and assistance from teachers, the learning resources function as learning toolkits for students, providing procedures, instructions, and other information to support the learning process (DepEd Order No. 018, 2020).

There is no doubt that the COVID-19 pandemic has altered the educational landscape. Nonetheless, the DepEd is hopeful that the BE-LCP could hold the key to delivering high-quality basic education that is adaptable and accessible in the new normal, even in the face of diverse socioeconomic circumstances that impact the ability of families to provide learning support at home and the unique needs of individual students.

Alongside these significant changes, the new normal in education has brought about a move away from in-person instruction toward a variety of learning delivery methods, including online learning (De Villa & Manalo, 2020). According to Llego (2020), distance learning refers to the method of instruction delivery in which students and teachers interact virtually although being geographically apart. It is not a new phenomenon; rather, it dates back to the introduction of the mass-produced printed publications and the development of the contemporary postal system. Well-crafted remote learning initiatives have the potential to enhance accessibility to education for a wider range of students by being both efficient and convenient. This may seem difficult without learners and teachers interacting in a classroom, but learners enrolled in distance learning programs can learn just as much away from a classroom as in one (Loveless, 2020).

Since most educational systems are required to implement substitutes for in-person instruction, the Department of Education (DepEd)

implemented DepEd Order No. 18 series of 2020, also known as "Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan." As a result, many educational systems have shifted to an online format to continue teaching considering school closures (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2020). Consequently, it became increasingly difficult for teachers to provide a basic, high-quality education due to the shift from in-person instruction to modular remote learning.

Accordingly, Tuhian Elementary School has selected the printed version of the learning delivery modality stated above. Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) were given to students enrolled in the printed modular learning program offered by DepEd. Weekly Home Learning Plans (WHLPs), which list the lessons and assignments that students must complete each week, were also sent. It is the duty of the teachers to keep an eye on the students' progress, since they may contact them via phone, text, or email. If at all feasible, the teachers will visit students at home who require support or remediation.

On the other hand, there are a few challenges that teachers encounter, especially with SLM distribution and retrieval, learning assessment, feedback mechanisms, and intervention strategies. The study's conclusions provided pertinent data that were utilized as a guide to create an enhanced coping mechanism framework that will enhance the way that teaching is delivered in the setting of the new normal.

Research Questions

The study generally aimed to investigate the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms strategies employed by elementary school teachers of Tuhian Elementary School in the implementation of MDL in the new normal. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the experience of elementary grade teachers in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in the new normal be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. distribution and retrieval;
 - 1.2. assessment of learning;
 - 1.3. feedback mechanisms; and
 - 1.4. intervention strategies?
2. How may the coping mechanism strategies employed by elementary grade teachers to address the challenges they encountered be described?

Literature Review

Implementation of Modular Distance Learning

One type of distant learning that has been found to be effective for providing basic education during the COVID-19 pandemic is modular learning. According to Ambayon's (2020) study, modular instruction is more effective than traditional teaching methods since it allows students to progress at their own pace. It is unrestricted self-learning panache in which learners are stimulated and develop interest by quick reinforcement and comments to practice exercises. When instruction is delivered in this way, students take ownership of their education because they already know all they need to know and can study without the aid of textbooks or other learning resources (Casiple, 2020). Teachers need to be knowledgeable about this method of teaching because it involves individualized instruction and allows students to use SLMs in print or digital format (electronic copy). These SLMs are compliant with K–12 standards and contain a comprehensive learner engagement in the task anchored on the MELCs, which were carefully considered essential to learn during the crisis.

SLMs are Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) learning resources that are developed in accordance with standards and quality-assured to guarantee that MELCs are met within a specified time frame. DepEd commissioned a team of subject-matter experts who worked as authors and validators in the central, region, and division offices to create the materials (Division Memorandum No. 161, 2020). To guarantee that the learners' new experience with the learning modality is appropriately transitioned both at home and in school, school administrators, teachers, and community partners are expected to provide adequate and appropriate guidance and support (Regional Memorandum No. 0375, 2020). Considering the process of teaching and learning, students are given an estimated amount of time to complete the activities that have been allocated to them. To guarantee that learners have secured mastery of the learning contents—a crucial requirement for success in the subsequent module—flexibility in completing each module is granted to learners based on their learning needs, characteristics, and level of understanding (Division Memorandum No. 201, 2020). Teachers who are unfamiliar with MDL, however, could run into some problems and difficulties.

Challenges in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning

The following issues with modular distance learning were noted in the Labrado et al. (2020) study: (a) learners' abrupt transition from in-person instruction to modular distance learning with very little student engagement; (b) parents juggling work and being a learning facilitator at home; (c) a slow internet connection or lack of internet signal that makes it difficult for teachers and parents to communicate effectively; (d) teachers and school administrators lacking the necessary training to implement printed modular distance

learning; and (e) unfocused students experiencing high levels of anxiety. Even when both educators and students are making every effort to perform effectively in this setting, difficulties are unavoidable because MDL has several shortcomings when it comes to the actions that follow.

Distribution and Retrieval. Even though the parents were given access to and clarity regarding the timelines for SLM retrieval and distribution, most of them disregard them. As a result, teachers were required to report to schools needlessly while they were going back and forth to amuse the parents. Given the possibility of a COVID-19 pandemic, this posed a serious risk to their health (Melorin, 2020). Similarly, Castroverde and Acala (2021) assert that instructors' problems with module distribution are related to late module claims and trouble getting in touch with parents and students.

In the meantime, learners' obligation to adhere to all the conditions outlined in their activities is linked to teachers' difficulties in recovering the SLMs. The teacher's schedule for reviewing SLMs is impacted when the deadline for submission is missed. Additionally, because some students fail to include their names when submitting, teachers have difficulty identifying SLMs. Traceability of learners completed SLMs presents a barrier for teachers as they divide up the SLMs. In addition to SLMs without names, some students send in responses that are not fully completed. This does not only pose a challenge on teachers' responsibility in monitoring the learners' performance, but also a struggle on teachers seeing a learner not learning anything from school due to the challenges posed by the delivery of instruction in the new normal (Castroverde & Acala, 2021).

Assessment of Learning. The wide range of topic areas and learner ages in the K–12 curriculum creates a complex web of requirements. The interactive cycle of teaching and learning is enhanced by real-time formative and summative evaluations, which are challenging to do in remote learning. It is difficult to transfer differentiated instruction for students who are second language learners or who have other supports in place in a physical building to online or modular distance learning systems. Learning is a collaborative process in which students develop their language and social-emotional skills. In distant learning, this process appears very different and yields various outcomes (Guisinger, 2020). Since preservice instructors were not educated in this medium, it can be challenging to think of creative ways to implement various evaluation procedures. Since distance learning cannot offer real-time supervision from a teacher or facilitator when administering exams and creating outputs, validity and reliability of students' responses may also become a problem (Laghigna, 2020).

Feedback Mechanism. Because MDL mostly depends on the abilities of More Knowledgeable Others (MKOs), also referred to as the adult figures in the learners' households, it is in peril. To teach the learners, the topics they do not comprehend, the module depends on their expertise and patience. This may not be too much of an issue in most middle-income households where at least one member has attended college. However, this could not be the case for lower-class households that are struggling to make ends meet, don't have any college graduates, and have both parents absent. Learners would undoubtedly struggle to comprehend their lectures without MKOs who can clarify the concepts in the modules (Estrada, 2021).

The numerous problems that these changes placed on them were beyond the capabilities of either the parents or the teachers. While instructors struggled to maintain relationships with their students and missed guidance and support from their schools, many parents encountered unstructured task transmission by teachers and a lack of teacher feedback (Goetz, 2020). If children were educated at home, there would likely be more of a learning gap between families with high and poor socioeconomic statuses because of variations in living arrangements, instructional materials, and time availability.

Intervention Strategies. Every student enters the learning spaces with a different set of requirements, knowledge, abilities, and personalities, claims Pappas (2015). Because of this, differentiation makes it challenging for teachers to provide specialized instruction, particularly when leading multiple classes with many students. These data point to the necessity of using intervention techniques to deal with these issues in the way that teaching is delivered. Teachers will tailor lessons to meet the needs of remote learners. While some lessons call for group work, others call for in-depth conversation. Additionally, it is much worse for pupils who are having difficulty and require more help and support. According to De Villa and Manalo (2020), differentiating lessons necessitates the use of materials and resources that enhance conceptual comprehension. However, this cannot be provided at home for all aspects of learning. Teachers must use intervention tactics as a result, which can be difficult considering the new normal. On the other side, using coping mechanism methods is one of the most efficient ways to handle the difficulties listed above.

Coping Mechanisms to Address the Challenges in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning

Teachers need to have hope despite the obstacles the pandemic has brought about in the classroom. In these unpredictable, depressing, and volatile times, they must be adaptable in their pursuit of delivering high-quality education. Educators need to embrace all of these to improve standard practice and deal with the "new normal."

Maintain a Positive Well-being. Teachers' good health has a favorable impact on learners' academic progress and well-being, which in turn boosts work satisfaction and productivity (Spilt et al., 2011). Additionally, studies show that raising student achievement enhances school wellbeing and raises teacher well-being raises learning results. Teachers can carry out their tasks and responsibilities in spite of the difficulties of these difficult times when they maintain a positive outlook, a healthy lifestyle, and reduce stress.

In addition to improving academic achievement, teachers who cultivate a good environment and nurture self-care can also help students

make progress in their social and emotional development outside of the classroom (Loveless, 2020).

Practice Being Resilient. Resilience among teachers is essential to ensuring the effectiveness of instruction delivery in the new normal since resilience is the capacity to overcome adversity. It is one of the essential components of success and a skill for handling challenges that are unavoidable. Resilience, according to Herrmann et al. (2011), is the capacity to constructively adjust, preserve, and reclaim mental health under trying circumstances. It is essential for educators to give students a remarkable, high-quality education. Teachers need to be resilient for the following reasons: (a) the teaching profession demands high levels of intellectual and emotional labor; (b) there is a high prevalence of work-related stress, anxiety, and depression in academia; and (c) supporting teachers' resilience helps them recover from traumatic situations. Realizing that developing students who can overcome obstacles and setbacks is a key objective of education leads to emphasizing resilience in the teaching and learning process.

Improve Time Management Skills. The technique of effectively allocating time for tasks and activities that are necessary for the success and advancement of an organization is known as time management. The creation and execution of a schedule, assignment of subjects, total number of periods taught by teachers, lesson planning, regularity, and punctuality of teachers in the classroom, pre-planning of class activities, individual counseling and guidance from teachers, scheduling of time for students, and planning and preparation of extracurricular activities for students are all included (Sahito et al., 2020).

Intensify Collaboration. In general, collaboration refers to people or groups working together to solve issues and produce results that are difficult or impossible to accomplish when done alone. Organizations find collaborative connections appealing as the combined efforts of individuals and their skills yield greater benefits due to the recognized synergies. Collaborative advantage is the term used to describe the superior benefits produced by teamwork (Australian Research Alliance for Children and Youth, 2013). Considering the new normal in education, wherein schools are resource-constrained and cannot meet every requirement of instructors, gaps are continuously filled through collaboration with stakeholders and community engagement. According to the guidelines in DepEd Memorandum No. 53 s. The school fortifies its collaboration to assist the BE-LCP until 2020, or the Joint Implementing Guidelines on the 2020 Brigada Eskwela and Oplan Balik Eskwela Relative to the COVID-19 scenario, and the Adopt-a-School Program under the Republic Act No. 8525. To create relevant learning experiences for everyone, collaboration is an essential tool. Parents who are aware of their children's needs are more likely to offer assistance and support, which in turn makes teachers more accountable for giving their students high-quality instruction. In this instance, creating learning opportunities involves everyone. The use of learning modalities becomes organized and simple when everyone is aware of their duties and responsibilities (Okai-Ugbaje et al., 2020).

Methodology

The study utilized a phenomenological approach to investigate the challenges encountered and coping mechanism strategies employed by the public elementary grade teachers in the new normal. It was conducted in Tuhian Elementary School. The DepEd's guidelines and memos, especially those on flexible learning and materials as outlined in DepEd Order No. 21, s., are rigorously adhered to by this research location. 2019 or the K–12 Basic Education Program Policy Guidelines, which lays out adaptable learning materials that consider the needs, context, situations, and diversity of learners. Accordingly, six participants in this study were selected through purposive sampling based on the following criteria: (a) they are elementary school teachers; (b) they work at Tuhian Elementary School; (c) they use MDL as a learning delivery modality; and (d) they had to be willing to take part in the research.

This study utilized a self-devised semi-structured interview guide as its research instrument. It is divided into two parts, the first of which consists of questions designed to identify the difficulties faced by elementary school teachers when implementing MDL in relation to distribution and retrieval, learning assessment, feedback mechanisms, and intervention strategies. The questions in the second section, on the other hand, are designed to investigate the coping mechanisms that primary school teachers use to deal with problems and difficulties when implementing MDL. Four master instructors who hold a Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) degree validated the research instrument to verify its validity as a data gathering tool. The observations and suggestions of these experts were incorporated in the final production of the instrument.

After the instrument was validated by the above-mentioned experts, the interview was accomplished based on the given appointment of the six participants. During the interview, the interviewers informed the participants that it would be concluded with overt-recording to accurately capture the verbal responses. Conversely, they were allowed to request that the recording may be paused at any time and may also choose to leave if they feel the need to. After the interview, the recorded responses were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted to provide answers to the questions posed in this undertaking using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Meanwhile, this research project followed specific guidelines to protect the informants' rights. It has first considered the idea of participation that is optional. Nobody was forced to take part in this project. Considering this, informed permission was necessary. Second, the study's anonymity was assured. The informants' entire sharing of information was handled with the highest confidentiality and would not be disclosed to anybody not directly associated with the study.

Results and Discussion

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in the New Normal

Table 1. *Issues and Challenges Encountered by Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in Terms of Distribution and Retrieval*

Responses	Codes	Categories	Theme
Participant 1. "Sometime Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) has no answers. As well, they do not submit it on time".	Insufficient answers	Insufficient response	
Participant 2. "There are Learning Activity Sheets where the responses do not match the handwriting of the assigned students."	Unmatched handwriting	Unparallel handwriting	Challenges in distributing and retrieving SLMs
Participant 4. "The common difficulties I have encountered in the distribution and retrieval of SLMs ay poor internet connectivity".	Poor internet connectivity	Internet connection	
Participant 5. "Minsan nawawala ang ibang modules. Incomplete ang SLMs na nakakarating sa school. Siguro ay napapabayaang na".	Incomplete SLMs	Misplaced SLMs	

The summary of challenges encountered by elementary grade teachers in the implementation of MDL in the normal in terms of distribution and retrieval is shown in Table 1. The responses suggest that there are inevitable challenges regarding the distribution and retrieval of SLMs. As confirmed by participants 1 and 2:

"Sometimes, parents return and pick up the new modules late. Based on my experience, this poses a challenge for us teachers and for the students as well because we are unable to check them immediately, preventing us from providing timely feedback."

"There are Learning Activity Sheets where the responses do not match the handwriting of the assigned students. This poses challenges because we cannot determine whether the learners are learning something from the modules or not."

The findings can be supported by the study of Talain et al. (2023) who concurred teachers in public elementary schools faced a variety of problems and difficulties when implementing MDL in the new normal. The distribution and retrieval of SLMs, evaluation of learners' progress, use of feedback mechanisms, and use of intervention techniques were the criteria used to identify these issues. Incongruence, the following were the typical issues encountered: SLMs submitted after the deadline, LASs without names, misplaced SLMs, inadequate training leading to ignorance, uncooperative parents, and a deficiency of communication channels.

Furthermore, teachers also encounter challenges related to poor internet connectivity and misplaced SLMs. The participants supported such statement by confirming that:

"One of the challenges I encountered in the Modular Distance Learning (MDL) setup is poor internet connectivity. It is difficult to coordinate with parents who cannot receive modules when they are not reachable. Sometimes, they are not interested in addressing concerns."

"More often than not, there are incomplete Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and Learning Activity Sheets (LASs) that are returned to the drop boxes. Even if I check other boxes in different sites, I still cannot find them. Perhaps, when learners are delayed in accomplishing learning tasks in the modules, they choose not to submit them. At times, they simply hand them over to a parent leader who is not assigned to their specific site, leading to misplacement."

The study of Castroverde and Acala (2021) support the aforementioned claims. They contend that students' obligations to fulfill all the conditions outlined in their activities are linked to teachers' difficulties in assigning and retrieving the SLMs. Additionally, some parents provide inactive contact information that negatively impacts the time allotted for the distribution and retrieval of the SLMs, and other parents do not respond to the teachers' inquiries. Additionally, because some students fail to include their names when submitting, teachers have difficulty identifying SLMs.

Table 2. *Challenges Encountered by Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in Terms of Assessment of Learning*

Responses	Codes	Categories	Themes
Participant 2. "The challenge that I have encountered was on how to implement formative assessment."	Utilizing assessment	Problems in facilitating assessments	Challenges in the assessment of learning
Participant 4. "Summative test paper arrive at the drop boxes without any answers".	Summative assessment		
Participant 6. "Before the start of the School Year 2020-2021, we did not receive sufficient training on facilitating assessment strategies in Modular Distance Learning (MDL)."	Lack of training	Insufficient training	

The summary of challenges encountered by elementary grade teachers in the implementation of MDL in the normal in terms of assessment of learning is shown in Table 2. As the results suggest, there were difficulties in employing formative assessment and summative assessment. These difficulties may be rooted due to lack of training on facilitating assessment strategies in the context of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) modality. This is supported by participants 2, 4, and 6 by explicating that:

"The challenge I encountered was in evaluating learners through formative assessment. I didn't know how to facilitate it, and I also had no idea how to ensure the validity of the students' answers. Additionally, I was not sure how to ensure that they take the formative tests seriously".

“The students are having difficulty answering the summative test, which often leads them to leave it unfinished, negatively impacting their performance. They seem unconcerned, even if some parts of the summative test remain unanswered. It is okay for them to submit it to drop boxes without providing answers”.

“The absence of adequate training left us fumbling for effective assessment methodologies to ensure the validity of students' responses. We often found ourselves at a loss, unable to monitor students in real-time to prevent cheating or to confirm the authenticity of their work”.

Guisinger (2020), who asserts that the wide age range of students and topic areas in the K–12 curriculum generate a complicated web of requirements, supports the results. The interactive cycle of teaching and learning is enhanced by real-time formative and summative evaluations, which are challenging to do in remote learning. Meanwhile, Laghigna (2020) claims that it is difficult to think of ways to adopt various evaluation methodologies because preservice instructors were not taught in this type of modality.

Table 3. *Issues and Challenges Encountered by Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in Terms of Feedback Mechanism Strategies*

Responses	Codes	Categories	Themes
Participants 5. “Some parents are not positively responding sa feedback na ibibinigay ng guro sa kanilang anak. Malahaga na they are interested kase sila ang magreiterate nun sa kanilang mga anak considering the fact na sila ay ang tinatawag na More Knowledgeable Others (MKOs).	Unparticipative parents	Difficulties in feedbacking	Challenges in employing feedback mechanism strategies
Participants 3. “Some parents do not have cellphone or Fb account that is why it is hard to implement the feedback mechanism strategies”.	Lack of communication tools	Insufficient Communication channel	
Participants 6. “Mahina ang internet connectivity. Yun ang pinakamatinding challenge na kinaharap namin sa pagimplement ng feedback mechanism strategies”.	Poor internet connectivity	Internet connection	

The summary of challenges encountered by elementary grade teachers in the implementation of MDL in the normal in terms of employing feedback mechanism strategies is shown in Table 3. Most of the problems were found to be caused by parents who were unresponsive and uninvolved. Furthermore, inadequate internet access and a deficiency of communication instruments, like Facebook accounts and telephones, are the other obstacles impeding the execution of the feedback mechanism techniques. This is supported by participants 2, 4, and 6 by stating that:

“Some parents are indifferent; they do not positively respond to the feedback provided about their children, even though they play a significant role in relaying it to their kids for academic improvement”.

“Implementing a program becomes challenging when most parents lack communication tools. Contacting them becomes a substantial challenge since many of them do not use cellphones, and they cannot be added to a Google Classroom group because they do not have Facebook accounts”.

“Some parents have complete gadgets, but their internet connectivity is weak, so it remains a challenge on how to inform them about the feedback”.

The claims corroborate Estrada's (2021) study, which concurred that MDL is in peril since it mostly depends on the abilities of More Knowledgeable Others (MKOs), also referred to as the adult figures in the learners' households. To teach the learners the topics they do not comprehend, the module depends on their expertise and patience. This may not be too much of an issue in most middle-income households where at least one member has attended college. However, this could not be the case for lower-class households that are struggling to make ends meet, don't have any college graduates, and have both parents absent. Learners would undoubtedly struggle without MKOs who can clarify the concepts in the modules.

Table 4. *Challenges Encountered by Elementary School Teachers in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in Terms of Intervention Strategies*

Responses	Codes	Categories	Themes
Participant 2. “One of the common problems that I have encountered is time constraint sa pagimplement ng intervention program because of too many reports in school”.	Ancilliary tasks	Time constraint	Challenges in employing intervention strategies
Participant 5. “Lack of communication channels is definitely the root of challenges I encountered in utilizing intervention strategies”.	Lack of communication tools	Communication channel	
Participant 6. “Ang problem na naencountered namin sa pagconduct ng aming Visita Eskwela Program, which is our intervention program was the yung layo ng mga bahay ng aming mga estudyante”.	Vast distance from school	Distance	

The summary of challenges encountered by elementary grade teachers in the implementation of MDL in the normal in terms of utilizing

intervention strategies is shown in Table 4. As the results suggest, the following are commonly encountered problems: time constraints, lack of communication channels, and vast distance from school. These problems negatively impact the implementation of the intervention strategies. This is supported by participants 2, 4, and 6 by explaining that:

“Time constraints pose a challenge in deploying effective intervention strategies. Balancing the urgency of addressing student needs with limited time creates pressure among us. Swift and targeted interventions become crucial, demanding efficient planning and execution to maximize impact within the constraints of a tight schedule”.

“Inconsistent or inaccessible channels hinder timely updates, hindering collaboration between teachers and parents. Establishing effective lines of communication becomes pivotal, ensuring crucial information reaches the right parties for successful intervention implementation”.

“In implementing our program, Visita Eskwela, we encountered difficulty as some students' homes are too far. They cannot be reached through our means of transportation”.

Every student enters the learning spaces with a different set of requirements, knowledge, abilities, and personalities, claims Pappas (2015). Because of this, differentiation makes it challenging for teachers to provide specialized instruction, particularly when leading multiple classes with many students. These data point to the necessity of using intervention techniques to deal with these issues in the way that teaching is delivered. Teachers will tailor lessons to meet the needs of remote learners. While some lessons call for group work, others call for in-depth conversation. Additionally, it is much worse for pupils who are having difficulty and require more help and support. Intervention programs are helpful in this regard to address such issues. Conversely, given the new normal, putting it into practice appears difficult.

Coping Mechanism Strategies to Address the Difficulties in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in the New Normal

Table 5. Coping Mechanisms Strategies Employed by Elementary School Teachers in the Implementation of MDL

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Participant 1. “For me being optimistic in this time of pandemic is beneficial”.	Positivity	Maintaining positive well-being	Coping Mechanism Strategies
Participant 4. “We must practice being resilient”.	Resiliency	Practicing being resilient	
Participant 5. “We must fortify our collaborative efforts”	Intensify collaborative efforts	Intensifying collaboration	

Table 5 provides an overview of the coping strategies used by elementary school teachers to deal with the difficulties arising from implementing MDL in the new normal. The findings imply that having an optimistic outlook is a useful coping technique. Most importantly, teachers' good health has a favorable impact on learners' academic progress and well-being, which in turn boosts work satisfaction and productivity (Spilt et al., 2011).

This is supported by participant 1 who confirms that:

“For me, the most effective coping mechanism in these times of uncertainties and collective trauma is to remain positive. Being optimistic during this pandemic is beneficial as it helps in personal improvement. At the same time, it enables us to deliver effective and efficient instruction despite numerous challenges.”

Loveless (2020) asserts that when educators cultivate a good environment and develop self-well-being, this can lead to greater academic achievement as well as social and emotional growth among students outside of the classroom.

In this regard, it was also agreed with that resilience is another useful coping method. Resilience, according to Herrmann et al. (2011), is the capacity to constructively adjust, preserve, and reclaim mental health under trying circumstances. It is essential for educators to give students a remarkable, high-quality education. This is supported by participant 4 who confirms that:

"It is believed that Filipinos are resilient because even in the face of disasters or tragedies, we remain resilient and capable of facing challenges. I believe that educators, as catalysts of change, must practice resilience because it contributes to the success of delivering instruction in the new normal."

Numerous obstacles have emerged in the framework of the "new normal," changing the face of education as it exists now. Educators' resilience has been characterized by their commitment to teaching, learning, and development over the years. The educators who are thriving in these difficult times and who have grasped the concept of resilience are those who are pushing forward, fearless of change and danger, and actively seeking out opportunities for professional growth (O'Scanail, 2020).

Conjointly, collaboration was also utilized as coping mechanism. As shown in the table, it has specified the importance of having sound and open communication in these times of adversity; for, it was helpful in attaining the tasks associated with the objectives of the

school. Participant 5 supported this by emphasizing that:

"In our school, we applied social coping because we believe that, in this time of the pandemic, collaboration is essential. We prioritize open communication, which is effective in engaging with learners, parents, and co-teachers. Through collaboration, we have more successfully attained the objectives specified in our Learning Continuity Plan."

Australian Research Alliance for Children and Youth (2013) corroborates the findings, stating that organizations are drawn to collaborative relationships because the synergies that result from pooling resources and expertise yield benefits that are larger than those attained through individual efforts. Collaborative advantage is the term used to describe the superior benefits produced by teamwork. Similarly, Okai-Ugbaje, et al. According to al. (2020), cooperation is essential for producing relevant learning opportunities for all. Parents who are aware of their children's needs are more likely to offer assistance and support, which in turn makes teachers more accountable for giving their students high-quality instruction. In this instance, creating learning opportunities involves everyone.

Conclusion

In light of the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. (1) Elementary grade teachers faced various challenges in the implementation of MDL in the new normal. These challenges were determined by on how they distribute and retrieve SLMs, evaluate the progress of students, and employ intervention techniques and feedback mechanisms. In congruence, the following were the typical issues that were encountered: (a) late submission of self-learning modules and learning activity sheets; (b) missing self-learning modules and learning activity sheets, (c) tracking and assessing the development of learners through summative and formative evaluation, (d) ignorance brought on by inadequate lack of communication channels, (e) uncooperative and unresponsive parents, and lack of training inadequate internet access, (f) time constraint, and (g) distance from school. These challenges negatively impact students' academic advancement. (2) Elementary grade teachers utilized coping mechanism strategies to address the challenges they encountered in the implementation of MDL in the new normal. In connection, being optimistic, resilient, and enhancing collaborative skills are some of the effective coping mechanisms employed by teachers. These helped them be more flexible as they strive to provide the quality education in these times of uncertainties, despair, and fraught.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby given. (1) School administrator must provide teachers with relevant capacity enhancement program to help them be well-versed with MDL as a potent learning delivery modality. Further, they should promote positive well-being resiliency, and collaboration. (2) Teachers must continuously employ various coping mechanism strategies, which are proven effective to help them address the challenges they encounter. (3) Parents must communicate to the teachers openly. Effective communication between teachers and parents is relevant for successful implementation of MDL. Regular updates, clear instructions, and a collaborative approach foster understanding and support. This synergy ensures a conducive learning environment, bridging the gap between educators and parents for the benefit of students. (4) The future researchers may use the current study as a guide in the improvement of the implementation of MDL. In regard, In conjunction, this undertaking can serve as an underpinning in exploring the challenges encountered and the coping mechanism strategies used by junior and senior high school teachers in the implementation of MDL.

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